

Corpus-based Automatic Identification of Multi-word Entry Candidates

Pavel Rychlý, Miloš Jakubíček

MASARYK
UNIVERSITY

Brno, Czech Republic

eLex 2019 collocations workshop, Sintra, Portugal

For many languages: problem solved, despite issues

- tokenization
- part-of-speech tagging
- lemmatization
- collocations
- thesaurus
- ...

- but: single words are a virtue out of necessity
- Sinclair's idiom principle (1991):

"the principle of idiom is that a language user has available to him a large number of semi-preconstructed phrases that constitute single choices, even though they might appear to be analysable into segments."

- most NLP is still single-word based, not multi-word based
 - becoming more multi-word based, which implies using more data, might be more viable than any neural network progress

- for all languages: a beast in the game
 - or was it *A Pain in the Neck for NLP* (Sag, 2002)
- big manifestation of low agreement in linguistics
- what are they, actually?

Multi-word expressions

constituent phrases, named entities (person names, organization names, geographic names), proper names, collocations, idioms, n-grams, skip-grams, lexical bundles, chunks, clusters, phrasemes, compounds, sem-grams, free order expressions, fixed expressions, semi-fixed expressions, syntactically-flexible expressions, institutionalized phrases, phraseological units, light verb constructions, proverbs, multi-word terms, ...

Classification

“The classification of MWEs is a challenge. Even more so, as there is no general consensus about what counts as an MWE.”

(Sailer & Markantonatou, 2018)

- polylexicality
 - easy (oh wait, German!)
- fixedness
 - morphological
 - syntactic
- compositionality/idiomaticity
 - purely semantic or cultural, etymological, ...

All language specific!

Searching corpora for MWEs

- polylexicality
 - well defined word units (tokens)
 - issues: CJK, Lao, ...not using white space; compounding (German)
- fixedness
 - morphological: PoS taggers, lemmatizers
 - syntactic (word order, discontinuity): grammar
- compositionality/idiomaticity
 - how to detect?
 - the context of the MWEs diverging from the context of its words

All language specific!

- to find a particular MWE
- to show MWE candidates
 - by frequency or some saliency score
 - lexicography

- of utmost importance from lexicographic perspective
- ⇒ which MWEs should go into a general language dictionary?
- could it be detected automatically?

Easy options

- wordlist, n-grams
- ⇒ not sufficient
- collocations
- ⇒ not sufficient, but ...

modifiers of "box"			
<input type="checkbox"/>	po PO Box	31,202	9.64 ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	p.o. P.O. Box	30,275	9.62 ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	dialog dialog box	24,664	9.33 ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	ballot at the ballot box	18,862	8.87 ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	search the search box	30,782	8.84 ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	text the text box	20,033	8.52 ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	set-top set-top boxes	11,853	8.3 ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	check check box	12,527	8.18 ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	cardboard cardboard boxes	10,829	8.15 ...
<input type="checkbox"/>	black black box	18,501	7.92 ...

nouns modified by "black"

hole

49,091

9.9

black hole

hair

18,629

8.42

black hair

man

40,612

8.32

black man

bear

11,873

8.02

black bear

pepper

10,863

7.97

black pepper

box

18,501

7.92

black box

The obvious solution:

- compare contexts of *black*, *box* and *black box*
- big differences suggest non-compositionality
- which contexts?
- how to compare?

- compare the context of the multi-word bigram with the contexts of its both components
- given a bigram multi-word AB consisting of words A and B , x being the first word to the left and y being the first word to the right, then for every x and y we calculate counts of xAB , xA , xB and AB_y , A_y and B_y .

- shall the multi-word bigram behave compositionally, there should be a high overlap for each x between xAB and either xA or xB , and similarly for every y between ABy and Ay or By
- for *black hair*, the collocate *shiny* would go with *black hair* just as it goes with *black* and the collocate *curly* would go with *black hair* just as it goes with *hair*.

Distributional compositionality scoring III

- we measure this overlap by taking the average *keyness* over all x and y
- the *keyness* is calculated as the maximum of two ratios p/q and q/p , where p and q are relative collocation (cooccurrence) counts of the bigram multi-word and the single word, respectively
- p is the bigram count, q is the closest of x_A , x_B or $x_{_A}$ to p if p is smaller or bigger than all these three values, otherwise $p = q$.
- the higher this score is, the higher the non-compositionality would be.

Compositionality: *black*

Bigram multi-word	Score
black pepper	23.5
black box	11.5
black market	11.4
black hole	8.2
black leather	4.6
black hair	3.0
black voters	2.4
black man	2.2

Compositionality: *hole*

Bigram multi-word	Score
watering hole	15.9
ozone hole	14.2
black hole	8.2
rabbit hole	2.2
gaping hole	1.9
bullet hole	1.8
drilled hole	1.2

Compositionality: conclusions

- new feature in Sketch Engine soon to be
- large corpus required (hundreds, better thousands of hits for the bigram needed)
- extensions to more than two-word units possible

Bonus part: a multi-word thesaurus

- one based on word sketches: soon in Sketch Engine too
 - one based on word embeddings calculated using FastText
- ⇒ <https://embeddings.sketchengine.co.uk>,
and here: [multiword models](#)

- solutions for finding MWEs largely available, more to come
- homework for linguistics: simpler classification of MWEs
- my hope for the future: more scientific approaches for inclusion of MWEs into dictionaries